

Multimodal grasp planner for hybrid grippers in cluttered scenes

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Abstract—Grasping a variety of objects is still an open problem in robotics, especially for cluttered scenarios. Multimodal grasping has been recognized as a promising strategy to improve the manipulation capabilities of a robotic system. This work presents a novel grasp planning algorithm for hybrid grippers that allows for multiple grasping modalities. In particular, the planner manages two-finger grasps, single or double suction grasps, and magnetic grasps. Grasps for different modalities are geometrically computed based on the cuboid and the material properties of the objects in the clutter. The presented framework is modular and can leverage any 6D pose estimation or material segmentation network as far as they satisfy the required interface. Furthermore, the planner can be applied to any (hybrid) gripper, provided the gripper clearance, finger width, and suction diameter. The performance of the system has been assessed with an experimental campaign in three manipulation scenarios of increasing difficulty using the objects of the YCB dataset and the DLR hybrid-compliant gripper.

Index Terms—Grasping; Grippers and Other End-Effectors; Perception for Grasping and Manipulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous and reliable robotic grasping is a desirable functionality in robotic manipulation, as it is required for a broad range of applications including pick and place in service robots, logistics, and manufacturing [1]. Autonomous grasping of a variety of objects is a complex problem due to its multidisciplinary nature, involving end-effector design, perception, planning, and control to guarantee a reliable and robust grasp of the target object. Manipulating objects with different shapes, sizes, surface properties, and weights using a single end-effector is not a trivial problem. The dominant end-effectors used in industry are suction and parallel-jaw grippers, due to their simplicity, precision and low control complexity [2]; however, each modality has its own drawbacks. A promising venue is the design of an end effector combining multiple grasping modalities, which would allow handling different kinds of objects.

This work presents a novel multimodal grasp planning framework for hybrid grippers that exploits only geometrical (3D bounding box) and material information of the objects [3]. The grasping pipeline takes as input the RGB and depth

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Fig. 1. Examples of different grasping modalities offered by DLR HCG. First row: two-finger grasp, two-finger grasp on a wide object, single suction grasp. Second row: double suction grasp on a single heavy object, double suction grasp on two different objects, magnetic grasp.

images, and outputs the best grasp among the possible grasping modalities, depending on the arrangement of the objects in the scene.

Differently from other approaches that are designed for a specific (hybrid) gripper or that train an end-to-end network combining different stages like object pose estimation and grasp planning into one stage, including gripper-specific parameters, the presented framework is general and modular, having the advantage of allowing replacement of one module without affecting the others, and is applicable to different hybrid grippers. The planner has been developed for dense clutter and bin-picking scenarios and exploits a neural network for obtaining the 6D pose (translation and orientation) of the objects in the scene and another network to infer the surface properties of the objects using an RGB-D image. Any pose estimation networks that give as output a 3D bounding box or material segmentation methods that provide the 2D mask of the metallic objects can be used. The advantage of the proposed solution is that the method is general and can exploit the latest improvements in computer vision by just changing the backbone modules. Furthermore, it does not need specific training to be adapted to other grippers. In addition, as the grasping pipeline uses only geometrical information provided by the pose estimation module, it has a low computational cost, and is fast compared to other grasp pipeline approaches. In contrast to other works, the approach considers finger joint configuration in the planning framework, in case that the gripper offers multi-DoF fingers, allowing it to adapt for grasping objects of different sizes even in cluttered scenarios. Furthermore, besides the two-finger and single suction grasps present in existing literature, double suction modality for big and/or heavy objects and magnetic grasps for metallic objects

(Fig. 1) are considered.

An experimental campaign has been conducted to assess the performance of the proposed planning framework on the objects of the YCB dataset [4].

II. GRASPING PIPELINE

The proposed grasp pipeline (Fig. 2) takes as input the RGB and depth images, the 3D bounding boxes of the detected objects as given by a pose estimation network, the mask of the metallic objects as given by a material segmentation network, the URDF of the gripper, and optionally, the CAD models of the objects for precise filtering of grasps.

Each detected object is modeled as a set of 9 points: 8 corners and the centroid. For the cuboid, each face can be defined as a set of 4 points, where the face center for object i is computed as $\vec{c}_k^i = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{j=1}^4 \vec{p}_{kj}^i$, with k representing a face of the cuboid. The faces relevant for grasping are the ones that are visible from the camera's viewpoint. Therefore, for a generic object i , it is possible to define a set of upward faces that satisfy the following condition: $\mathbb{F}_u^i = \{f_k^i : \theta_k^i < \eta\}$ where $k = 1, 2, \dots, 8$, and θ_k^i is the angle between the vertical vector $-\vec{z}$ and the face normal (Fig. 3). The condition is satisfied if the angle is below a given threshold η (which has been set to 30° for the experiments). The normal \vec{n}_k^i is computed as $\vec{v}_{k1}^i \times \vec{v}_{k2}^i$, where $\vec{v}_{k1}^i = \vec{p}_{k4}^i - \vec{p}_{k1}^i$ and $\vec{v}_{k2}^i = \vec{p}_{k2}^i - \vec{p}_{k1}^i$ (Fig. 3). Thus, after normalizing the normal $\vec{n}_k^i = \frac{\vec{n}_k^i}{\|\vec{n}_k^i\|}$, θ_k^i is obtained as $\arccos(\vec{n}_k^i \cdot -\vec{z})$.

A. Grasp synthesis

Each upward face i is then sampled to find potential two-fingers grasps and suction grasps. A two-finger grasp can be defined as a set of a translation vector, rotation matrix, and the required gripper opening needed for grasping the target object. The rotation is represented as a 3×3 matrix where the column vectors are the axis, binormal, and approach orthonormal vectors. Therefore, with Fig. 3 as reference, for a two-finger grasp, $\vec{approach}_{ks}^i = -\vec{n}_k^i$ and $\vec{axis}_{ks}^i = \frac{\vec{v}_{ks}^i}{\|\vec{v}_{ks}^i\|}$. The binormal is the cross product between the other two vectors: $\vec{binormal}_{ks}^i = \vec{axis}_{ks}^i \times \vec{approach}_{ks}^i$. The subscript $s = 1, 2$ represents the two sides of the face, since the two-finger grasp can potentially occur along both axis directions. Thus, both sides are sampled starting from the center of the face along the axis direction with a given stride $d = g\lambda$, where $g = \{0, 1, -1, 2, -2, \dots, \frac{dim_k^i}{2}, -\frac{dim_k^i}{2} : dim_k^i < \xi\}$. λ has been set to 10 mm for the experiments, while ξ is the maximum gripper clearance. Hence, the translation vector of a possible two-finger grasp is derived as $\vec{t}_k^i(d) = \vec{c}_k^i + d \cdot \vec{axis}_{ks}^i$. It is worth noticing that a side of an upward face is sampled only if the dimension dim_k^i of that side is smaller than the gripper opening, and the $opening_k^i$ is set to dim_k^i . Being $R_{ks}^i = [\vec{axis}_{ks}^i{}^T \quad \vec{binormal}_{ks}^i{}^T \quad \vec{approach}_{ks}^i{}^T]$, the set of all the possible two-fingers grasp is defined as $\mathbb{F}_a^i = \{\vec{t}_k^i(d), R_{ks}^i, opening_k^i\}$.

A suction grasp can be defined with a translation vector and an approach direction. The set of possible suction grasps

is computed by sampling the upward face in a circular manner starting from the center (\vec{c}_k^i). The translation vector of a possible suction grasp is derived as: $\vec{t}_k^i(r, \gamma) = \vec{c}_k^i + r \cos(\gamma) \vec{v}_{k1}^i + r \sin(\gamma) \vec{v}_{k2}^i$, with $r = m\delta$ and $\gamma = n\rho(r)$, where $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \frac{\min(dim_{k1}, dim_{k2})}{2}$, δ is a fixed quantity set to 10 mm in the experiments, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 360$, and $\rho(r) = \frac{60}{r}$, defined as function of r to have an homogeneous sampling independent of the distance to the center. Also for suction grasps, the approach direction is opposite to the normal of the face: $\vec{approach}_k^i = -\vec{n}_k^i$. The set of all possible suction grasps is formed as: $\mathbb{S}_a^i = \{\vec{t}_{kg}^i, \vec{approach}_k^i{}^T\}$.

B. Refinement and filtering

Depending on the arrangement of the objects in the scene, not all the predicted grasps are feasible, and up to now, the grasps are generated considering the dimension of the cuboids and not the actual size of the objects. Therefore, a refinement process to match the actual size of the objects in the grasp positions and a filtering stage to keep only the feasible grasps are needed. By using the depth information and silhouette of the object, more accurate gripper contact points touching the surface of the objects can be estimated. The feasibility stage removes grasps that belong to parts of the object that are invisible to the camera and are occluded by other objects in the scene. In order to compute the visible region of an object, the CAD model is projected in the depth image through a render pass knowing the object's 6D pose and the camera's intrinsic parameters. The pixels of the projected mask that are near the corresponding values of the depth image within a given threshold, which can be tuned depending on the accuracy of the depth sensor, are considered visible. Figure 4 gives an example result of the procedure.

A two-finger grasp can be executed only if the gripper can move deep enough along the approach direction to make contact on the object's side. Therefore, performing a feasibility check to verify if there is enough space for the fingers without colliding with the surrounding objects is crucial.

For suction grasps there is no need to refine the gripper opening, and the feasibility check to ensure enough space for the fingers is also not applicable. However, a feasibility check is required to verify that the suction cup can adhere to and seal completely on the object's surface. This is achieved by checking if a circle with a radius of the suction cup adequately fits inside the visible silhouette of the object. The feasibility filtering stage concerning occlusion parts of the object is the same as for two-finger grasps. Figure 5 graphically explains the feasibility concept.

C. Grasp selection

After computing the two-finger grasps and suction grasps, it is possible to assign a score to objects and grasps based on desired heuristics to select the grasp for execution. Each score is a numerical value between 0 and 1. The scoring for objects is based on the depth, the visibility percentage, and the number of collisions with other objects. In cluttered scenes, objects at the top are preferred, as they are less occluded by other objects.

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the grasping pipeline for two-finger, suction, and magnetic grasp modes. The diagram shows the modularity of the design and flow of information. The input images (RGB and depth) are fed to the two backbone networks for pose estimation and metallic segmentation. Optionally, depending on the employed networks, a pose estimation adjustment and the mask check can be applied, respectively. Then, the grasps are computed. The two-finger grasps are refined using the available CAD models of the object or the raw depth information. The two-finger and suction grasps are filtered based on some feasibility criteria. Finally, after a scoring stage, the best grasp candidate is selected. It is worth noticing that for better visualization, two different image scenes are shown for the two-finger and suction grasps and for the magnetic grasp.

The visibility score of an object takes into account how much it is visible in the clutter by considering the percentage of visible pixels. The collision score considers for each object the number of collisions with other objects, privileging the ones that have fewer collisions.

For assigning a grasping score, the relevant metrics for both two-fingers grasp and suction grasp are the distance to the barycenter and the numerosity. The first is meant to privilege grasps that are near the center of the object, to improve the stability of the grasp. The numerosity is included considering that if one grasping mode has very few feasible grasps even with a poor barycenter score, then maybe it is possible that also the remaining ones are not so robust, thus, it is better to prefer the other modality. Such a score is simply obtained as the cardinality of the resulting feasible grasps over the total number of grasps. The selected grasp is the one that has the highest total score among the two modalities and belongs to the target object (in case there is a specific object to be grasped).

Besides the normal suction grasp mode, where only one

Fig. 3. Left: 6D bounding box representation of an object i . The points p_j^i , $j = 1, \dots, 8$ are the vertices expressed in the camera frame O_c and f_k^i , $k = 1, \dots, 6$ are the faces that constitute the cuboid. Right: Face k of an object cuboid i , composed of 4 points. The two dimensions of the face are dim_{k1}^i and dim_{k2}^i . The vectors v_{k1}^i and v_{k2}^i are used to compute the vector normal to the face n_k^i .

Fig. 4. Result of the visibility computation process. In the left image, the Cheez-it box is occluded by the tomato soup can, the Spam meat, and the Mustard bottle. This occlusion is reflected in the right image, obtained by projecting the CAD model in the depth image for the computed 6D pose. White pixels are considered visible for the next steps in the pipeline.

Fig. 5. Grasp feasibility check. Left: example of the process that checks if there is enough space for the two fingertips (represented as two black and white rectangles) to afford in depth. Right: an example of the process that checks if there is enough space for the suction cup (represented as a circle) to completely adhere to the object surface.

suction cup is used, the planner also considers using both suction cups at the same time for heavy or big objects. In that case, the translation vector of the grasp pose coincides with the center of the upward face, and the rotation matrix is built similarly to the two-finger grasp mode; in such a way the binormal is parallel to the major axis of the face, the approach is opposite to the face normal, and the axis is derived as the cross product between the other two. Then, the suction cups are placed on the surface with an approach perpendicular to the object, having a distance of $dim/4$ from the center on each side. If the two suction cups lay on a visible portion of the object, such a grasping mode is preferred over the single suction mode. For grippers with multi-DoF fingers, such as the DLR HCG, an inverse kinematic (IK) is required for positioning the fingertips at the desired pose or, for the two-fingers grasp, for getting the specified opening. Kinematic

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS FOR THE FOUR DIFFERENT SCENARIOS

Scenario	success rate	# two-fingers	# suction	# double-suction	# magnetic
Structured clutter	97%	35	16	10	3
Dense clutter	87.5%	15	5	4	0
Bin clutter	63%	8	3	5	0
Double objects	98%	0	0	6	0

feasibility is an additional filter used to eliminate non-feasible grasps.

The magnetic mode is meant for thin metallic objects, and is selected when the height and size of the metallic object fulfills a predefined threshold. The metallic mask provided by the material segmentation network is double-checked with the contours of the object retrieved in the depth image to have a better segmentation mask. Indeed, it is not an easy job deriving the material properties of an object from an RGB image, and the accuracy of the existing methods is not so high. The centroid of such a refined mask is re-projected from the 2D image to the 3D camera coordinate system using the intrinsic matrix, and is used as the translation vector for the magnetic fingertip.

When a suction cup is available on each finger, such as in the DLR HCG, it is also possible to grasp at the same time two objects using the two suction cups even if the two target objects have different heights, compensating for such a difference with the DoF of the fingers. In this case, the translation vector of the grasp pose is the middle point between the two center points of the two upward faces involved in the task. The rotation matrix has the binormal computed as the normalized difference vector between the two center points, the axis as the cross product between the binormal and the approach vector of the suction grasp in the face center point, and the approach the cross product between the other two. The fingertip placement is handled by the IK solver, which also checks if the configuration is feasible or not.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION AND DISCUSSION

Four manipulation scenarios of increasing difficulty are created using the YCB objects. The robot should grasp the items from a table and transport them to a storing area. Demonstration videos can be found at the following [video link](#)¹.

For magnetic grasps, metallic objects should be detected and segmented. For this purpose, the Material In Context (MINC) dataset is used for training the network, and the approach presented in [5] is implemented.

For the experiments, the DLR Hybrid Compliant Gripper (HCG) has been used as a gripper, the Deep Objects Pose (DOPE) network [6] as a pose estimation network, and GoogLeNet opportunely modified as a material segmentation network that can recognize metallic objects [7] trained on the Material In Context (MINC) dataset [5]. Other equivalent backbone networks can be employed as long as they provide the 6D pose or the bounding box (cuboids) for the objects for the pose estimation stage (e.g. [8]), and the mask that identifies metallic objects, required for the magnetic grasps.

¹<https://github.com/SalvatoreDAvella/Multimodal-grasp-planning.git>

The proposed multimodal grasp pipeline has been tested in several scenarios: structured tabletop with sparse clutter, dense clutter, and bin-cluttered scenes. Each of the three scenarios introduces a different level of difficulty to test the ability of all components in the grasp pipeline. Other scenarios for the simultaneous suction grasp of two objects were considered to show additional capabilities of the grasping pipeline.

Table I summarizes the results obtained during the experiments for the different scenarios. The table reports the grasping success rate taking into account all the system's components, starting from the grasp pipeline prediction to the execution of the grasping action by the gripper and the movement of the robotic arm, in order to measure the performance of the pick and place robotic system. For the conducted tests, the planner always provided the correct target and grasp according to the selected metrics when the vision module detected an object. The average object pose estimation time required by the selected vision module DOPE is 1.1s, while the average time required by the grasp planner for returning the grasping pose and modality for the next target is 1.8s in scenes containing ten objects.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Autonomous grasping of a variety of objects is still an open problem in robotics, especially for cluttered scenarios. This work presented a novel multimodal grasp panning algorithm for hybrid grippers that allow multiple grasping modes. The presented framework is general as it can be used for other hybrid grippers, and it is also independent of the networks used for the 6D pose estimation and material segmentation. The performance of the system has been assessed with an experimental campaign in different manipulation scenarios on the objects of the YCB dataset.

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